

Segregation of four M₄ male-sterile lines. IRRI, 1978.

Designated male-sterile line	Pedigree	Fertile (no.)	Sterile (no.)	Total (no.)	(X ²) ^a 3:1
ms-a	E2-3-10	209	80	289	1.00
	E2-3-10	207	75	282	0.38
	E2-3-11	214	83	357	0.58
	E2-3-11	349	108	457	0.45
Total		1039	346	1385	0.00
ms-b	E2-538-6	199	69	268	0.08
ms-c	E6-953-10	196	58	254	0.64
ms-d	E6-1335-5	217	64	281	0.74

^a X² = table value for a df (5%) = 3.84.

was controlled, the F₁ plants were completely fertile. That indicates the

recessive nature of male sterility, which was also confirmed in the M₄, as all the

Isolation of tall and dwarf seedlings of rice

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In the segregating populations of dwarf-tall crosses, isolation of the dwarf seedlings from the tall in the nursery offers certain testing advantages. Failure to separate the dwarfs from the tall may ultimately result in extinction of the dwarf types or suppression of their performance. Therefore, preliminary tests were conducted to determine the association of certain morphological characters to aid in the selection of the dwarf types in the nursery. Eighty pure line rice varieties of diverse sources were

tested during boro (summer).

The number of leaves at 25 days after sowing (X₂) and at 35 days (X₃), and seedling length at 25 days after sowing (Y₁) and at 35 days (Y₂) were recorded. X₂ and X₃ were correlated with mature plant height (X₁). A significant positive association between X₁ and seedling characters X₂, X₃, Y₁, Y₂ was found (see table). X₂ and X₃ were also highly significant and positively correlated with Y₁ and Y₂. In 1970, W. L. Chang reported that seedling length was positively correlated with plant height, especially during early growth.

The results indicated that the dwarf types will have shorter seedlings that produce fewer leaves. Therefore, the

four male-sterile lines segregated in a 3-1 ratio (see table).

Incomplete panicle exertion was observed for lines ms-a, ms-b, and ms-d, but ms-c showed normal panicle exertion. That indicates that spikelets of line ms-c have a greater chance than the three other male-sterile lines of receiving pollen from the neighboring fertile plants. A single panicle per male-sterile plant was harvested to study the amount of outcrossing in male-sterile lines. Outcrossing was maximum for ms-c (33.6%), followed by ms-d (32.5%), ms-b (29.8%), and ms-a (14.8%). ■

number of leaves and elongation rate of the seedlings should be considered when separating the dwarfs from the tall in the nursery.

Correlation (r) values between mature plant height (X₁) and number of seedling leaves (X₂ and X₃) and seedling length (Y₁ and Y₂). Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Characters	r value
X ₁ X ₂	0.9730**
X ₁ X ₃	0.9637**
X ₁ Y ₁	0.9792**
X ₁ Y ₂	0.9700**
X ₂ Y ₁	0.9891**
X ₂ Y ₂	0.9658**
X ₃ Y ₁	0.9531**
X ₃ Y ₂	0.9818**

**Significant at 1% level of probability.

Four new rice varieties released in Nepal

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After intensive research on promising genotypes in Nepalese research stations and in farmers' fields for more than 4 years, the national seed committee has released 4 varieties for the tarai, inner tarai, and equivalent climatic regions of Nepal.

For the chaite dhan season (early crop, Mar-Jun)

1. *Laxami*, formerly IR206 1-628-1-6-4-3, from the cross IR833-6-2-1-1//IR1561-149-1/IR1737. The line was introduced into Nepal through the

International Rice Yield Nursery-Early (IRYN-E) in 1975. It matures in 111 days – one of the earliest cultivars released.

2. *Durga*, formerly IET2938 (Jaya//IR8/2*Latisail). Bred in India, the line was introduced into Nepal through the IRYN-Medium duration nursery in 1974.

For the barkhe dhan season (normal monsoon)

3. *Janaki*, formerly BG90-2 (Peta*3/TNI/Remadja) was developed in Sri Lanka and introduced into Nepal through the IRYN-M in 1975.

4. *Subitri*, formerly IR2071-124-6-4 (IR1561-228-1/IR1737//CR94-13), was introduced into Nepal through India's initial evaluation trial in 1975.

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Yield performance at different Nepalese research stations, agronomic characteristics, and responses to diseases and insects of 4 new rice varieties in Nepal, 1978.^a

	Laxami	Durga	Janaki	Sabitri	Panvanipur-1 (check)	Chandina (check)	Masuli (check)
<i>Mean yield (t/ha)</i>							
Kankai	5183	5923	4323	3703	5736	4697	3121
Tarhara	6060	6284	5286	3918	6914	5990	3854
Janakpur	4128	5098	4717	4893	4585	4243	4797
Parwanipur	4585	4974	3883	3405	4362	3915	2548
Rampur	2800	3429	4001	4053	3949	3000	3164
Bhainva	4758	4477	3905	4196	2922	5430	3240
Nepalganj	5113	4696	5126	3722	5861	4708	4042
Av	4777	5016	4404	3995	4804	4794	3564
<i>Agronomic characteristics</i>							
Days to heading	88	100	104	90	106	111	121
Days to maturity	111	128	134	120	135	140	150
Plant ht (cm)	93	91	92	80	98	94	120
Tillers (no.)	6.5	6.5	7.0	8.0	9.0	9.0	9.5
1,000 grain wt (g)	23	25	26	20	27	25	17
Milling recovery (%)	72.5	66.5	—	70	67	73	—
Head rice (%)	79.0	86.5	—	81.9	79.9	91.8	—
Protein (%)	6.9	1.3	—	7.0	5.5	8.0	—
Grain quality	Coarse	Medium	Coarse	Medium	Coarse	Medium	Medium fine
<i>Response to diseases^b and insects^c</i>							
Blast	1	1	1-2	1-5	1-3	1-3	1-6
Bacterial blight	3-5	3-5	7-9	3	1-3	3-5	3-5
Brown spot	3	3	3	3	1-3	1-7	3-5
Sheath blight	—	MR	—	—	MS	—	—
Brown planthopper	MR	S	S	—	—	R	—
Green leafhopper	R	R	S	—	—	R	—
Gall midge	—	MR	—	—	MR	—	R

^aVarieties Laxami and Durga were tested in Mar-Jun along with check varieties Parwanipur-1 and Chandina; Janaki and Sabitri were tested against Masuli (Mahsuli) during Jun-Nov, the normal season.

^bOn a scale of 1-9 of the 1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

^cMR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, R = resistant.

Laxami and Durga yield better than the recommended varieties in the early season, and their early maturity leaves farmers enough time to grow a second

crop. The two also have better resistance to insects and diseases than other recommended varieties. Durga and Sabitri have good eating quality and

medium-fine grain. All four varieties have high response to fertilizer, lodging resistance, and improved plant type (see table).■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Cooking characteristics of selected IR424 lines

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Basmati rice is well known for grain and cooking qualities and for aroma. It is used in the preparation of delicacies on festive occasions and its long grain brings a special market price; however, it has poor plant type and yields low.

Crosses were made during the mid-1960s at IRRI to improve its plant type and thus its yield potential, while keeping its other qualities intact.

From materials originally received from IRRI, 119 lines of the IR424 cross (Basmati 370*³/TN1) were selected at BRRI. The lines were grown in observational trials in the 1978 boro (Dec-May) at BRRI. Fifteen lines were selected for their grain yield and cooking quality. Cooking quality was further evaluated on the basis of elongation ratio

(av length of 10 randomly selected cooked grains to av length of 10 randomly selected uncooked grains), imbibition ratio (vol of cooked to vol of uncooked grains), visual scoring of cooked grains, and aroma.

Twenty-five polished grains were cooked for 7 minutes in 20 ml boiling water. The cooked grains were transferred to petri dishes and visually scored for uniformity of length and smoothness. The cooked samples were also checked for aroma. BR5, BR7, and Kataribhog